

Controlled-release of carvacrol oil from stimuli-responsive copper doped mesoporous silica particles

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Abstract:

Microbial colonisation of surfaces forms a dangerous reservoir for pathogens contributing to the spread of infections which can cause significant cost to human life and the economy at large. There is a tangible need for innovative antimicrobial coatings that are highly effective, safe, self-disinfecting and removing bacteria, fungi and viruses more cost-effectively than current non-biodegradable, toxic, and fossil fuel-based coatings in use. RELIANCE project aims to design and develop smart response self-disinfectant antimicrobial nanocoatings based on a new range of smart antimicrobial nanoparticles.

These particles consist of copper doped mesoporous silica particles (CuSMIN) modified with biobased bioactive compounds as carvacrol, which are essential oils (EOs) coming from non-edible plants. To achieve better control of the EOs release, the CuSMIN surface is modified with stimuli-responsive polymer brushes, which are organic molecules that exhibit different polymer chain conformation upon external stimulation as temperature (T) and pH [2]. Among others, (2-(dimethyl amino)ethyl methacrylate) monomer (DMAEME) is selected for the functionalization of CuSMIN surface as it responds to both pH and T. These brushes are grown from CuSMIN via surface-initiated atom transfer radical polymerization (SI-ATRP), which is one of the most effective methods to synthesise polymer brushes on particles surfaces [3]. The PDMAEME brushes onto CuSMIN surface are characterized in terms of fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), elemental analysis and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) to confirm the modification of CuSMIN surface (CuSMINpolyDMAEMA). The variation of particle size, obtained by dynamic light scattering (DLS), also indicates the presence of polymer brush shell, which respond to external stimulus as pH and temperature. At ambient temperature, increasing the pH, the average diameter decreases,

meaning that at protonated state ($\text{pH} > \text{pK}_{\text{aPDMAEMA}}$), the polymer brushes are probably in their open conformation, while at non-protonated state ($\text{pH} < \text{pK}_{\text{aPDMAEMA}}$), the polymer brushes seem to be in a collapse conformation. At constant pH, increasing the temperature, the average diameter decreases.

Regarding the release of the carvacrol EO, pH responsive behaviour of PDMAEMA brushes grafted on CuSMIN was investigated to ensure the control leaching of this specie into the environment to fulfil the main objective of the RELIANCE project. The release was followed in real-time using an electrochemical reagent-free paper-based device, which has been already employed for a wide variety of essential oil detection [4]. Upon monitoring the electrochemical response up to 60 minutes, the sample exhibited a clear oxidation peak, indicating the carvacrol release from the particles during the first 60 minutes.

Keywords: smart antimicrobial particles, stimuli-responsive polymers, copper doped silica particles, essential oil.

References:

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